

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF POLICIES AND REGULATIONS IMPACTING SUPPLY CHAINS

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Introduction

Recent supply chain disruptions (e.g., Covid-19, Ukraine war, climate change) have triggered a new wave of policy interventions with policymakers accelerating their responses in a variety of ways from import/export bans to fiscal regulations and due diligence acts (Botwright and Verghese, 2022). In the EU for example, new rules will require companies to disclose information on their environmental and social impact, and failure to comply could result in fines or legal action. In Germany, the newly introduced Supply Chain Due Diligence Act requires companies to check supply chains especially for potential violations of human rights (Rowell, 2023). Similar regulations are also taking place in other countries of different continents such as Canada (Phillips, 2022). Following these regulations, some major car manufacturers such as Mercedes-Benz, BMW, and Volkswagen are being accused of failing to take appropriate measures (Schappert, 2023).

Changes in regulations and government policies can have a dramatic and large-scale impact on supply chains, however, research in this field is scant and our understanding of the actual consequences of the policies and regulations (P&R) is limited. Current research focuses on policy instruments and processes of specific countries or regions, but the modern nature of global cross-border chains requires a more integrated approach and more evidence on the associated implications of the various country specific P&Rs (Jiang et al., 2021; Tuominen et al., 2022).

This paper attempts to address this gap by conducting a systematic literature review (SLR) of recent peer reviewed articles and grey literature (e.g., policy documents). The aim of this research is to provide a comprehensive review of the regulations and policies introduced worldwide and analyse the key implications for supply chains. This research seeks to address the following questions:

RQ1. What P&Rs globally are in place to cope with supply chain disruptions?

RQ2. How can these P&Rs help to alleviate the pressures on modern supply chains?

Methodology

We have adopted SLR to have a comprehensive view of the global P&R landscape and its direction over the last ten years. Compared to a traditional literature review, SLR is more robust and transparent and summarises existing information in a thorough and unbiased manner (Tranfield et al., 2003).

The research protocol followed in this review was adapted from Tranfield et al., (2003) and started with a scoping study that informed the research question. Keyword groups (i.e., strings) were formed (S1 for policy-related keywords, S2 for supply chain context, and S3 for disruption-related keywords). Keyword strings were gathered and combined with the 'AND' operator (Figure 1) to search Scopus for articles and Google for grey literature in separate instances.

A list of criteria was considered during the scientific study selection process. Only articles and reports from 2013 were considered relevant owing to the recency of P&Rs. From 2013, 38 sources in English on P&Rs introduced by major countries and trading blocs were included. Authors also expected to see insights about the implications of mentioned P&Rs on supply chains in the sources. In addition to the 38 selected sources, three reports and five news articles were included from the grey literature as a result of reference snowballing which increased the total number of sources to 46.

This study is an attempt to categorise P&Rs with respect to their targeted megatrend themes. Kalaitzi et al. (2021) offers a framework followed by a PESTLE analysis. This paper adopts that strategy and following the selection process, through a thematic analysis, the megatrends of these P&Rs were identified for categorisation purposes. Finally, the implications of these P&Rs were discussed under separate supply chain sub-sections.

Figure 1: The systematic literature review process

Overview of megatrends and relevant P&Rs

As stated in the methodology chapter, this paper adopts the categorisation strategy of Kalaitzi et al. (2021) to identify the megatrends of each P&R (Table 1).

Name of P&Rs	Name of country / trading blocs	Aims / details	Megatrend theme
Corporate due diligence in supply chains	EU, Canada	To improve protection of human rights among the global supply chains (e.g., preventing child and forced labour and banning substances harmful to environment)	Environmental, social, governance
Automotive policy	Canada, USA, Mexico (CUSMA)	Tariff-free treatment to ensure most parts of the passenger vehicles and lights trucks are produced in the region	Electrification of transport
Manufacturer subsidy program	Honk Kong, Japan, Germany, Italy	Temporary manufacturer subsidy to increase mask availability	Catastrophic events
Price control policy	Italy, China	Temporary face mask price control to increase mask accessibility	Catastrophic events
Food security policy	China, Argentina, Italy	Temporary subsidies to agriculture (e.g., farmers, fisheries, processing companies) to restore food production and regulate food prices	Catastrophic events
Cybersecurity policies	China	Strengthen technological ecosystem to protect the nation, society, and supply chains	Cybersecurity
Rare earth stockpiling policy	China	Government built storage for rare earth elements and oxides	Resource scarcity
Rare earth export quota	China	Government restricted the export of rare earth elements	Resource scarcity

Rare earth export tax	China	Government increased taxes on valuable rare earth elements	Resource scarcity
Pig farm P&Rs	China	Temporary loan discounts and price control to ensure pork supply	Catastrophic events
Food safety policy	EU	To ensure a transparent risk assessment is being conducted in the entire supply chains rather than only 'from farm to fork'	Resource scarcity
Freight transport policy	Colombia	'Safe points' for drivers for disinfection and temporary suspension of toll collection for freight vehicles in national roads	Catastrophic events
Biofuels blending mandates	Global (especially EU)	To trigger a movement from fossil fuel to biofuel to reduce carbon emissions of transportation	Environmental, social, governance
Monetary covid relief policies	Eastern Europe and Asia (ECA)	Temporary wage subsidies, cash transfer, fiscal exemptions, and credit policies for companies	Catastrophic events
Agricultural promotion policy	Nigeria	Creating self-sufficiency especially for rice and wheat while developing vibrant export markets simultaneously	Protectionism and global trade shift
Framework for climate and energy policies	EU	To enhance low carbon energy systems to combat climate change	Environmental, social, governance
Biomass policy	UK	Funding with the ambition for the UK to become a sector leader in biomass production, and develop carbon offset market and UK timber for construction	Environmental, social, governance
Defense production act	USA	To temporarily taking the authority over the private sector in times of crisis to accelerate the development, manufacturing, and free-of-charge distribution of relevant products	Catastrophic events
Export license requirements	China	Certification to ensure that exported items meet quality and safety standards for reputational purposes	Consumer protection laws
The pacific trade alliance	Chile, Colombia, Mexico, Peru (Pacific Alliance)	Addressing frictions and harmonising technical standards in sectors such as cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and food to reduce the time and cost of trade	Supranationalism
Economic security promotion act	Japan, Korea	Subsidies for firms to relocate their production out of China and install new infrastructure to meet cybersecurity criteria	Protectionism and Cybersecurity
Emergency response	China	Temporary epidemiological investigations, social distancing, and quarantine mandates to stabilise and sustain manufacturing operations	Catastrophic events
Emission control areas policy	EU and USA	To control emissions from international shipping and limiting allowed sulphur content for ships in controlled areas of ports	Environmental, social, governance
Risk preparedness regulation	EU	Aims to establish EU energy markets and secure energy supplies	Environmental, social, governance
Agricultural policy	EU	To ensure fair income to farmers, preserve biodiversity, protect food and health quality, and act against climate change	Environmental, social, governance

Welfare and poverty alleviation programme	India, China, Nepal, Pakistan, Uzbekistan	Temporarily prioritise food availability and affordability through production and distribution incentives	Catastrophic events
U-turn law	South Korea	Subsidies and tax reductions for reshoring South Korean manufacturing companies involving better incentives for regional development (reshoring out of Seoul)	Protectionism
Tourism policies	Taiwan	To minimise the spread of Covid-19 and gain trusts of tourist to sustain tourism and hospitality industry	Catastrophic events
Forest investment program	Nepal	To reduce foreign imports and mitigate the impacts of climate change, incentivising forest land rehabilitation, improving private forestry, and creating rural jobs	Environmental, social, governance and global trade shift
Disaster risk management	Nepal	Adopting processes in infrastructure and construction to achieve sustainable development goals and create a disaster resilient Nepal (similar to Build Back Better Act of the USA)	Environmental, social, governance
Fashion sustainability and social accountability act	USA	Environmental and social disclosures (risks, actions to mitigate them, and measures to track results) for fashion retailers and manufacturers in supply chain	Environmental, social, governance
Free trade agreement	USA - Korea	Battery cells and packs for electric vehicles that meet the predefined regulations enter the USA tariff-free	Supranationalism
Modern slavery act	UK, Australia	To make the companies report on modern slavery risks in their operations and actions taken against them to protect human rights	Environmental, social, governance
Conflict minerals regulation	EU	Importers of elements such as tin, tungsten, tantalum, and gold should comply with social guidance of OECD	Environmental, social, governance
Plastic packaging tax legislations	UK	Extra tax for packages produced in or imported into the UK that contain less than 30% recycled plastic	Environmental, social, governance
CHIPS act	USA	Funding for semiconductor companies to manufacture chips domestically and reduce reliance on foreign-made semiconductors	Electrification of transport
Digital new deal and Green new deal	Korea	Increase employment and social safety net through building renovations, incentivising electric car production, and ensuring local development including digital and green initiatives	Electrification of transport
Inflation reduction act	USA	Incentives that aim to create new sustainable industries with cleantech such as green hydrogen	Environmental, social, governance
Bipartisan infrastructure law	USA	Incentives to replace value chains based on internal-combustion engines with electric and battery alternatives	Electrification of transport
G7 Clean energy economy action plan	EU	To enhance global resilience through supporting low and middle- income countries and incentivising a narrow set of sensitive technologies that could threaten peace	Technology development
Carbon border adjustment mechanism	EU	Aims to equalise the price of carbon in domestic products and imports so that EU climate objectives are not undermined through less ambitious non-EU countries	Environmental, social, governance

Alliance on processors and semiconductor technologies	EU	Focuses on identifying the gaps in production of microchips and expanding domestic production. Also includes stockpiling of significant products	Electrification of transport
Modern manufacturing initiative	Australia	Scaling up national businesses and integrate them into international supply chains (topics include space, medical applications, critical minerals, recycling, clean energy)	Global trade shift
Supply chain resilience initiative	Japan, Australia, India	Aims to jointly enhance use of digital technology in supply chains, share best practices, and support trade functions between the countries	Digital transformation
Semiconductor R&D fund	Taiwan	Fund to attract foreign companies to develop semiconductor R&D projects in Taiwan	Global trade shift
National environmental policy act	USA	To promote domestic lithium projects while ensuring a minimised negative environmental and health impact	Environmental, social, governance
Dual circulation	China	Make national manufacturing self-sufficient through less reliance on foreign technology	Protectionism

Table 1: Overview of P&Rs and their megatrends

Overview of the implications of P&Rs on supply chains

This chapter discusses the major implications of P&Rs in Table 1 on supply chains through three interrelated sub-sections to emphasise all these significant concepts separately.

Supply Chain Design

Following the pandemic and similar catastrophic events, protectionism has become a prevailing megatrend with companies now considering reshoring and friend-shoring in their supply chain design. Therefore, in response to covid; the United States, Japan, Korea, and many other countries are actively trying to reduce their dependence on certain countries (e.g., China) (Katada et al., 2023). World Trade Organisation (WTO) rules leave states with policy space to adopt certain kinds of P&Rs. Mostly adopted examples are subsidies for firms that diversify their supply chains geographically or adopt other kinds of regulations to bolster resilience (Meyer, 2020). Given that these types of subsidy flexibility are only provided during a crisis, reshoring production is not the lesson to draw from the catastrophic events, as that would be a costly exercise without the guarantee of improving supply availability with further shock hits.

Reshoring or renationalization comes with its own challenges and research by Kersan-Škabi (2022) has shown that there are implications for drop in welfare, GDP, and an increased supply chain vulnerability. A better solution would be to enhance the ability to source supplies rapidly and for firms, no matter where they are located, to respond in ease (e.g., The Pacific Trade Alliance). Catastrophic events have highlighted the importance of collaborative, extensive relationships with suppliers for supply chain resilience. (Botwright and Verghese, 2022). To spot the potential bottlenecks that impede the flow of supply, companies should develop systems to monitor market conditions (Findlay and Hoekman, 2021). For these bottlenecks, they need to proactively diversify the production and transportation when necessary and enlarge the supply chain to rapidly respond to changes in demand (Findlay and Hoekman, 2021; Kersan-Škabi, 2022). Companies can also prefer replacing long-distance imports/exports with those that are closest and regionalise the operations as much as they can (Kersan-Škabi, 2022). Therefore, diversification, collaboration, resilience, and regionalisation are processes which will be focused even more in the future.

Another potential impact of pandemic on supply chain designs are temporary takeovers as observed in the United States. 'Defense Production Act' which gives the president authority to require companies to accept "priority-rated" contracts, which were used for Covid-19 vaccines and creating a new supply chain from scratch. Thanks to the flexibility in their supply chain design, the United States became the first economy outside of China to make 100 million doses of vaccines publicly available (Bown, 2022).

Supply Chain Resource Scarcity and Security

Disruptions in trade flows and agreements also have a significant effect on security of supplies such as rare earth elements (REE) which are considered as strategic resources for supply chains. Imposing export or production quotas is justified as a response to market imperfections or on the grounds of protecting the environment and resources. Export controls can be counterproductive, as they can cause shortages of key inputs supplied by foreign companies, if they lead to tit-for-tat retaliation or emulation (Kersan-Škabi, 2022). Furthermore, quotas can impact prices negatively and put the entire global supply chain into risk. In such cases, there can be policies to ensure supply to domestic downstream industries. Particularly, WTO and international rules help to strengthen the supply, reduce prices, and strengthen the resilience (Mancheri et al., 2019). Alternatively, to ease the concerns about national needs and ensure adequate supplies of strategic resources, stockpiling became an essential P&R response in supply chains (Marcin, 2021; Meyer, 2020).

Another supply chain response to resource scarcity and ongoing environmental concerns is leaning towards renewable energies for sustainable supply chains. There are many incentives for the supply chains that encourage companies to use renewable energy and decrease overall carbon footprint (Azadeh and Vafa Arani, 2016; Gollakota and Shu, 2023). For example, Europe and India are developing policy initiatives (mainly mandates and incentives) and programs to counter China's leading position in lithium-ion battery production and to localise supply chains within their own regions. Further, governments and companies are investing in new battery chemistries to reduce costs, limit the use of sensitive raw material inputs, increase energy densities, and meet other needs ("Building Resilient Supply Chains", 2021).

Cybersecurity is another aspect to address for secure supply chains. There is supply, operational, and customer risks that can be attributed to cyberattacks. Some of these risks are theft of vendor credentials, breach from the vendor network, malwares and malfunctioning of the plant, intellectual property theft, and manipulation of data (Pérez-Morón, 2022). Supply chains should expedite the implementation of cybersecurity measures (e.g., Japan's Economic Security Promotion Act) to prevent potential disruptions ("Japan's Economic Security Promotion Act", 2022).

Supply Chain Social Sustainability

Social sustainability and human rights play a significant role in P&Rs. Main examples are supply chain and corporate due diligence acts, especially taking effect in the EU, that urges companies on regular evaluation of procedures, actions to prevent or mitigate relevant supply chain risks, and developing a system for monitoring measures implemented (Botwright and Verghese, 2022). Companies are expected to be in line with the Paris Agreement (limiting global warming) and publicly transparent in reporting including non-EU partners to comply with the EU due diligence act (Holger, 2023). Therefore, thousands of non-EU companies (e.g., American, British) will have to step up their sustainability reporting under EU rules, to increase visibility and transparency on everything from their greenhouse gas emissions to gender pay differences (Holger, 2023; Rowsell, 2023). Failing to comply could result in fines of up to 2% of their global turnover. Furthermore, it may cost the entire business relationship for the non-compliant companies (Rowsell, 2023). Thus, to achieve the desired outcome of contributing to social sustainability goals while maintaining efficient operations, the supply chains should be designed in a way which enables the internalisation of potential negative external issues without creating non-tariff trade barriers (Kolev and Neligan, 2022).

Finally, and obviously, catastrophic events also negatively influence social sustainability. Even in the presence of Covid-19 relief policies, a sharp reduction in physical and remote workers is observed in inefficiently designed supply chains (Wu, 2023). Therefore, the focus should be on the efficient design of supply chains (e.g., through digitalisation and automation if suitable) to be able to deal with these types of threats and disruptions without the negative social consequences.

Conclusions

At this moment, economies and societies are enduring several crises at the same time and this era of disruptions has negative and long-term humanitarian consequences. Climate change, the pandemic, wars, natural disasters, inflation, and trade disputes pose urgent questions that should simultaneously be addressed by supply chains. However, there is currently a lack of studies examining P&Rs imposed globally in the extant literature. To our knowledge, studies focus either on a country/region (Bown, 2022; Olomu et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2020) or on a certain type of supply chain such as maritime (Zavitsas et al., 2018) or manufacturing (Chen et al., 2023). This paper represents one of the first attempts to fill in this gap. This study is a first step towards understanding the effects of P&R on supply chains, and it encourages further research

to enrich our findings. Also, the emerging Table 1 links P&Rs to megatrends for a better understanding of P&Rs and their implications. As the modern supply chains are becoming more and more integrated, managers can prepare their companies to these implications even if such measures are not in place in their domestic supply chains.

There is a still underdeveloped potential of public-private collaboration to ensure resilience in supply chains. P&Rs play a significant role to manage and enhance the ongoing collaborations to develop robust supply chains. Therefore, a continuous wave of policy updates addressing the megatrends is key to resilient and sustainable supply chains. However, policymakers also should be attentive about how controlling they are on companies even in times of crisis (Rowse, 2022), to be able to efficiently dictate the supply chains. This paper can be helpful to policymakers by providing P&Rs throughout the world and the implications they bring to supply chains.

As with any study, there are limitations to this paper. Firstly, the research reviewed is based on two specific databases (Scopus and Google). Thus, its outcomes cannot completely reflect all P&Rs imposed by different nations and trading blocs against supply chain disruptions.

Future research can focus more specifically on trading blocs (e.g., EU, CUSMA) for deeper insights about the supply chains of those blocs. Likewise, a specific industry can be addressed to capture all the relevant P&Rs and their implications on the selected industry. Further, the areas where future policies will need to be developed to support resilience and effectiveness of supply chains can be identified. Finally, projections of potential P&Rs can be evaluated through scenario building and analysis including extreme and unforeseen scenarios. Even though it is often difficult to quantify the impact of P&Rs on supply chains, a quantitative analysis would be insightful both to managers and policymakers in the ecosystem.

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